

YOUTH VOICE JOURNAL™

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- Create knowledge and contribute to the literature by publishing high quality research on issues affecting young people
- Establish and further develop the youth-led method for research and social policy
- Provide a platform for the intellectual exchange of ideas around the globe with the aim of influencing policies and practices
- Actively encourage and aide those young people whose voice is rarely heard by policy makers and academia to be published

The Youth Voice Journal (YVJ™) a double-blind, peer-reviewed journal that publishes theoretical contributions and empirical studies on issues affecting young people worldwide.

The Journal publishes scholarly papers of the highest standard including: research papers, case studies, book reviews conference papers and proceedings. It has an international and multidisciplinary scope and is particularly interested in work that impacts on social policy and the law.

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